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prosumers for the energy **t**ransition

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP10 – Cooperation & collaboration activities

D10.3 – Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v3

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Abbreviations

BM	Business Model
CETP	Clean Energy Transition Partnership
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DMWG	Data Management Working Group
DoA	Description of Action
DR	Demand Response
EGVI	European Green Vehicle Initiative
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GBP	Generic Business Process
IoT	Internet of Things
LEC	Local Energy Community
LL	Living Lab
PC	Project Coordinator
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model
SLA	Service Level Agreement
TF	Task Force
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

BRIDGE is an important collaboration initiative within Horizon and more specifically high-TRL projects. Attempting to finetune research results and coordinate innovation strategies and frameworks, it manages to extract useful guidelines and contributions to energy system decarbonisation vision of the EU. ACCEPT will actively contribute to BRIDGE initiative and WP10 is dedicated in its larger part to this contribution.

ACCEPT will provide its methodologies and conclusions to the activities of business modelling in BRIDGE and will utilise conclusions on regulatory frameworks and data management. Additionally, the ACCEPT large scale validation testbed -which extends to various cultural, geographical and socioeconomic contexts- will constitute a valuable source of conclusion extraction that ACCEPT will share with other projects.

The project collaborative activities and participation in BRIDGE are monitored and reported in WP10 and more specifically in T10.1. The present deliverable is the third version out of four in total and includes the updated planning of relevant BRIDGE and synergies' activities, an overview of the activities carried out to date under the framework of WP10 and key next steps for the next period (between now and the next version of the deliverable).

Chapter 1 of the present document presents the scope and objectives of the task, the deliverable structure as well as its interdependencies with other activity lines of the project. It also includes a short section on the incremental changes and updates included in this report compared to the second version of the deliverable.

Chapter 2 includes all the ACCEPT collaboration framework as it has been laid out from the Grant Agreement stage and as it has evolved through the first semester of the project. Within the chapter, the management of BRIDGE participation within the consortium is presented together with the cooperation perspective with other H2020 projects. The main workshops, conferences and events that constitute suitable collaboration platforms are mentioned, such as Sustainable Places, etc.

Chapter 3 summarises the already assumed collaboration activities as conducted within M19-M30, including the BRIDGE General Assembly Meetings, Working Group discussions as well as knowledge sharing platforms established between ACCEPT and other projects of the call LC-SC3-EC-3-2020. A reference to planned activities for the next period is also presented.

Finally, **Chapter 4** includes the conclusions in the form of a brief summary of the document.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives of task

Given the constantly increasing importance of horizontal coordination between H2020 research and innovation projects and the optimal knowledge sharing in the fields of Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands, and Digitalisation, BRIDGE initiative will be considered a major part of ACCEPT project. Through the BRIDGE platform, ACCEPT will disseminate interim findings, conclusions and recommendations and at the same time it will analyse the feedback from other projects in order to enrich its knowledge base and spot potential complementarities. Work package 10 is devoted to the planning and monitoring of ACCEPT's participation in BRIDGE initiative as well as the preparation and coordination of synergetic events with "sister" projects.

More specifically, within the frame of task T10.1, active participation in BRIDGE working groups and tasks forces will be accomplished with special focus on prosumer engagement, demand response and energy communities. ACCEPT requires wide feedback in the areas of business modelling and EU regulation frameworks and, to this end, its participation in the respective working groups is essential. On the other hand, the wide-scale pilot activities in four different countries with numerous engaged users will comprise a significant testbed for framework validation resulting in important conclusions that could provide feedback to energy communities through relevant BRIDGE working groups and Task Forces. The above are only some indicative aspects of the ACCEPT project intended interaction within the BRIDGE initiative.

Task T10.2 will focus on the preparation, coordination and documentation of collaborative activities with synergetic projects within the H2020 frame. Common events and workshops will be coordinated, the results of which will be communicated to BRIDGE initiative but will be also utilized in the frame of dissemination and communication. Given the multitude of the different research and innovation projects, a convenient methodology in order to identify projects with common research grounds is through their corresponding topic IDs of the H2020 work programme. As per the task description, special attention will be given for the establishment of collaboration with projects such as DELTA, eDREAM, FLEXCoop, MERLON, WiseGRID, INSULAE, iELECTRIX, PARITY, FLEXIGRID, etc., where ACCEPT project partners were/are involved. Different approach will be adopted per project given that some of the abovementioned ones have been recently finalised. The projects that refer to the topic LC-SC3-ES-5-2018-2020 "TSO – DSO – Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation" will also be examined for synergies. The effort of coordination had already been established prior to the start of the project given that the consortia of INTERRFACE & CoordiNet had provided Letters of Intent for ACCEPT.

1.2. Structure of deliverables

Throughout the duration of the project, all activities of WP10 will be documented in four (4) deliverables starting from the present one. The first deliverable D10.1 has identified key subjects for synergies within BRIDGE and defined the basic collaboration roadmap within the project. The second and updated version of the report on collaboration activities between ACCEPT and other projects (D10.3), provides an update to the aforementioned schedule and collaboration roadmap and outlines the key collaboration and synergetic activities carried out between M19 and M30 of the project. The following and last deliverable (D10.4), will be an advanced version of the previous three reports, reporting all the implemented activities and updating the cooperation schedule up to the date of its submission. Table 1

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includes an overview of the deliverable together with a brief content description and their submission deadline. The deliverable responsible is the project coordinator (PC) and work package leader (WPL), Hypertech Energy Labs, utilising the essential contribution of the entire consortium in order to be able to exploit all the synergies' potential.

Table 1 Overview of WP10 deliverable reports

Del. No.	Description	Deadline
D10.1	Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v1	M6
D10.2	Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v2	M18
D10.3	Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v3	M30
D10.4	Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v4	M42

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

As described above, WP10 is extended throughout the project lifetime interacting with all involved activities given that it is focused on feedback collection for them and on the export of their findings into collaboration platforms. There is a special link between tasks 10.1 and 10.2 with the dissemination work package, namely **WP9 "Outreach activities for impact assessment"**. The participation in BRIDGE and the establishment of research synergies could be considered a type of dissemination. However, in the ACCEPT project, a distinction has been made between:

1. The dissemination of the results to pilot site stakeholders and the wider communication to the local communities, and
2. The interaction with research peers in terms of experience and knowledge sharing and the creation of strong Research & Innovation synergies.

Given the multiple aspects of dissemination and communication, the distinction in the two work packages facilitates the definition of different methodology approaches and adapts the activities accordingly.

Apart from the WP9, the **WP8 "Impact Assessment & Business modelling planning"** is closely linked to WP10 given that the interaction with BRIDGE will give attention to issues related to citizen engagement and energy communities, as well as barriers in terms of regulatory/ legislative frameworks and business models. Based on the work carried out by project representatives for the BRIDGE Data Management Working Group, there is a clear link between WP2 "Foundations" and WP10, as the Use Cases and Business Scenarios that will be tested/demonstrated within the project were fed into the group. Finally, **WP7 "ACCEPT Demonstration activities"** will be a direct source of findings and conclusions that the consortium of ACCEPT will contribute to BRIDGE elaborations. Figure 1 presents schematically the interdependencies between the different WPs of ACCEPT and the role of WP10 relative to the project elaborations.

Figure 1: ACCEPT Work Package interdependency Graph

1.4. Difference between D10.2 and D10.3

The main differences between this version of the report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative compared to the first version are as follows:

- The abbreviations table has been updated to be aligned to the current report version.
- Table 2 with the contact details of the current representatives of the project in the BRIDGE Working Groups and Task Forces¹ has been updated.
- Section 3.1 has been updated with information on the participation of ACCEPT in the BRIDGE General Assembly 2023 and all the activities carried out to date within the various BRIDGE Working Groups.
- Table 5 has been updated to include indicative BRIDGE Initiative meetings where ACCEPT participated for the period covered by the report, i.e., between M19-M30 (July 2022 to June 2023).
- Chapter 4 has been entirely updated compared to the previous version to cover the BRIDGE activities for the period between M19-M30. The structure remains the same but the content is completely different.
- The introduction, the conclusions and the executive summary sections have been slightly updated to fit to the new version D10.3.
- Two new Annexes have been added, including the presentations of the ACCEPT project at the ENLIT 2022 event and Sustainable Places 2023.
- Minor typos have been corrected, some updates in the already existing text have been made to align the text with the current version of the deliverable and timing of the project and a slight restructuring of the document has been implemented.

¹ Task Forces were not active for the BRIDGE initiative working period 2022-2023.

- The present section introduced in the previous version of the deliverable 10.2 with the main differences between D10.2 and D10.3 has been updated. The section helps the reader identify more easily the sections where key updates have been provided.

2. ACCEPT Collaboration framework

2.1. ACCEPT collaboration strategy and synergies within BRIDGE

BRIDGE initiative ranks amongst the most important ones especially for high-TRL H2020 projects in several different fields of Smart Energy Innovation. More specifically, as per the introductory declaration in its website, it constitutes an initiative of the European Commission that attempts to unify the H2020 research projects in Smart Grid and Energy Storage areas to build an organized view of horizontal and cross-cutting issues that are creating obstacle towards innovation².

The ultimate objective is knowledge sharing between the different activities, exchange of lessons learnt from the different demonstrators deployed in the projects and detection of similarities, overlaps or complementarities in the scientific methodologies. In order to better structure the discussion between the different projects, BRIDGE initiative has launched four (4) different working groups -as described in Figure 2- and three (3) Task Forces that intersect in between them. Each one represents a discussion group with partners that are participants and others that are responsible to organize the discussions. Some details on the scope of the working groups are mentioned as follows:

Figure 2 BRIDGE working groups. Source: [9]

WG1: Regulation

Regulation is a horizontal issue that is involved in many innovation projects since the smart energy future requires a renovation in the regulatory frameworks of the energy systems. To this end, the discussion focuses on two (2) axes:

- The analysis and promotion of recommendation punch lists on aspects such as the adoption of distributed and utility-scale energy storage. This issue involves several different aspects, such as the asset ownership, the business-market-financial conditions, different technical modalities such as grid characteristics, asset wear and tear, etc.
- The definition of incentives for demand- side management, smart metering and aggregation portfolios.

WG2: Data Management

² <https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/>

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In the frame of energy system digitalization and considering cybersecurity liabilities arising, as well as data protection provisions, data management appears to be another significant concept that affects multiple projects. The discussion mainly focuses on:

- The infrastructure issues in communication, the requirements in information exchange, the different use cases with focus on stakeholders, such as the system operators, etc.
- The integrity of data and the privacy preservation for customers.
- The analytics required for data processing, as well as novel data models that cover the new smart DERs interconnected in the system.

WG3: Consumer and citizen engagement

Given that the future energy scenarios involve demand response and locally balanced generation and demand resources, the role of prosumer engagement -both individually and as a member of an energy community- is crucial. Therefore, working group 3 focuses on:

- The creation of a unified consumer engagement approach through the different EU R&I projects.
- The investigation of the optimal approach for motivation of the consumers and the assessment of their active involvement in the energy market.

WG4: Business Models

The energy market is transitioning from a centralised one to an inclusive, multiple-stakeholder marketplace with a wide variety of interactions based on value chains. Thus, the respective working group is required to investigate certain business models and use cases that will combine value propositions and will promote market-based energy transactions. Although the BM WG has been inactive on 2020, from 2021 it has been reactivated.

Further to the working groups, BRIDGE internal structure has recently expanded with the addition of "Task Forces" [1] that are dedicated to more specific topics such as:

- i. Energy Communities
- ii. Scalability and Replicability
- iii. Joint Communication and R&I Priorities, etc.

The tasks forces were introduced in the 2019 BRIDGE General Assembly and intersect with the working groups as shown in Figure 3. Currently, some of the Task Forces are inactive and there is a chance that they might be terminated in due time. This will be updated in the next version of the deliverable.

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Figure 3 Overview of BRIDGE WGs & TFs. Source: BRIDGE

ACCEPT project aspires to actively participate in BRIDGE activities with the aim of joining forces with other H2020 projects and collectively contribute through new findings and demonstrations. From the beginning of the project, an in-depth analysis has been conducted to observe the BRIDGE TF/WG to which each activity of the ACCEPT project could contribute. This analysis has been done per Work Package and for each year of the project in order to better capture the common grounds. The results are presented in Figure 4, based on which the internal allocation regarding BRIDGE participation was conducted.

WP	BRIDGE Working Groups																BRIDGE Task Forces											
	Data Management				Business Models				Customer Engagement				Regulation				Energy Communities & Self-Consumption				Replicability & Scalability				Joint Communication/ R&I priorities			
	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4
WP1	x	x	x																									
WP2	x				x	x																						
WP3									x	x	x	x					x	x	x	x								
WP4	x	x											x															
WP5		x	x														x	x										
WP8					x	x			x	x			x	x														
WP9															x										x	x	x	x
Lead Partner	Hypertech, IsZEB				RINA-C				SIN				RINA-C				SIN				CIRCE, RINA-C				EEE			

Figure 4 Overlaps of BRIDGE WGs & TFs with ACCEPT research activities.

ACCEPT has created a wide spread validation framework including four (4) pilot sites that are or aspire to become energy communities. Each pilot engages numerous prosumers and business stakeholders in Demand Response practices and the project elaborations will focus on consumer engagement analysis, community mapping and Living Lab set-up in pilot sites. Through this process **ACCEPT will utilise feedback and best practices provided by BRIDGE WG on Customer Engagement. In parallel,**

it will provide these bodies with findings and conclusions created through the course of the project activities.

ACCEPT framework also includes real-time data collection as well as processing and curation of operational data of residences through IoT solutions. Specific tasks are dedicated to the creation of a Security Access Control framework for minimisation of security and privacy risks that facilitates bi-directional information flow. Based on these facts, **the active participation of ACCEPT project in BRIDGE Data Management Working Group is considered as strategically important.**

Last but not least, the construct of Energy Communities is quite new, which implies the need for elaboration on innovative business models that are prosumer-centric and offer compound Demand Response (DR) services. To this end, **the re-organisation of the BRIDGE Business Models Working Group is considered to be of strategic importance for ACCEPT** and that is the reason why the project will support it.

Overall, ACCEPT project intends to be in continuous interaction within but also beyond BRIDGE initiative with projects that focus on the same or neighbouring scientific fields. Therefore, it intends to create a high-level roadmap of activities that could reinforce the collaboration between projects and strengthen R&I synergies in order to enhance the quality of research outcomes.

Management of BRIDGE participation within the consortium

Based on the preliminary analysis of common grounds between the project activities and the BRIDGE focus groups, as presented in Figure 4, an internal allocation has been conducted so that ACCEPT follows-up all the Working Groups and Task Forces. Several members of the consortium will also attend (Hypertech Energy Labs, CIRCE, CERTH, RINA-C, SIN) the General Assembly with the coordinator having the responsibility of project representation. Table 2 includes the lead partners that have been allocated to the different BRIDGE Working Groups and Task Forces, as updated in year two of the project.

Table 2 Lead partners of ACCEPT project per BRIDGE WG & TF

BRIDGE bodies	Lead Partner	Contact Details of Responsible Person
Working Groups		
Data Management	Hypertech, IsZEB	i.dimitriadou@hypertech.gr p.valioli@iszeb.gr
Business Models	RINA-C	laura.bordo@rina.org
Customer Engagement	SIN, EEE	paul.tobin@smartinnovationnorway.com a.moser@eee-info.net
Regulation	RINA-C, CIRCE	laura.bordo@rina.org dmrivas@fcirce.es
BRIDGE Task Forces		
Energy Communities & Self-Consumption	SIN	paul.tobin@smartinnovationnorway.com
Replicability & Scalability	CIRCE, RINA-C	dmrivas@fcirce.es laura.bordo@rina.org
Joint Communication/ R&I priorities	EEE	a.moser@eee-info.net

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Beyond the plain participation in BRIDGE WGs and TFs, ACCEPT project has a strategic intention to be more involved in the organisation of the activities and the finetuning of the collective conclusions at BRIDGE level. Therefore, one of the ACCEPT consortium major partners, **RINA-C, co-chaired the Business Model Working Group in the first year of the project**, while **Hypertech Energy Labs, the project coordinator, has offered to be an “Active Contributor” in the Data Management Working Group.**

H2020 projects with strong collaboration perspective

Both within the frame of BRIDGE and beyond it, ACCEPT has launched an initial research of similar H2020 projects based on their corresponding topics and calls. Based on the Description of Action (DoA) provisions, the investigation initiated with topic ID **LC-SC3-ES-5-2018-2020** “TSO – DSO – Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation”. Table 3 below provides an overview of this investigation effort.

Table 3 Summary overview of H2020 projects linked to the topic LC-SC3-ES-5-2018-2020

Acronym	Title	Scope	Start date	End date
CREATORS	CREATIng cOMmunity eneRgy Systems	Support of technical, financial & social processes in Community Energy Systems (CES) in order to facilitate local stakeholders. The objective is to provide local CES agents with the capacity for high-quality simulation, etc.	1/9/2020	31/10/2023
ROBINSON	Smart integRation Of local energy sources and innovative storage for flexiBle, secure and cost-efficient eNergy Supply ON industrialized islands	Usage optimisation of local RES through the deployment of an integrated, smart and cost-efficient energy system coupling thermal and electrical networks, demonstrated in industrial environment in Norway.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024
REDREAM	REAL CONSUMER ENGAGEMENT THROUGH A NEW USER-CENTRIC ECOSYSTEM DEVELOPMENT FOR END-USERS ASSETS IN A MULTI-MARKET SCENARIO	The project aims to facilitate the participation of the prosumers in the energy market, based on an innovative Service Dominant Logic example.	1/10/2020	30/9/2023

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MAESHA	deMonstration of smArt and flEXible solutions for a decarboniSed energy future in Mayotte and other European isLAnds	The project aims to develop the required system flexibility, storage and energy management solutions to permit large-scale integration of RES.	1/11/2020	31/10/2024
IANOS	IntegrAted SolutioNs for the DecarbOnization and Smartification of Islands	The project is based on 2 Lighthouse islands (Terceira-PT, Ameland-NL) & 3 Fellow islands (FI) (Lampedusa-IT, Bora-Bora-FR, Nisyros-GR) in order to realise their joint decarbonisation and energy adequacy vision.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024
LocalRES	Empowering local renewable energy communities for the decarbonisation of the energy systems	The project develops a digital tool suite that enables social welfare through the energy community construct and with RES transformation.	1/5/2021	30/4/2025
eNeuron	greEN Energy hUbs for local integRated energy cOmmunities optimization	The project creates an innovative tool suite optimised operational aspects within local energy communities (LECs) with large-scale penetration of DERs and multi-scale energy network coupling.	1/11/2020	31/10/2024
VPP4ISLANDS	Virtual Power Plant for Interoperable and Smart isLANDS	The project objective is the enabling of RES integration, the fast-paced transformation to sustainable and digitalised energy systems in Islands through storage and consumer engagement.	1/10/2020	31/3/2024
REnergetic	Community-empowered Sustainable Multi-Vector Energy Islands	The project aspires to enable islanded energy systems or weak grids and non-interconnected systems to accommodate large shares of locally produced RES and comply with the Clean Energy Package provisions.	1/11/2020	30/4/2024

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OneNet	One Network for Europe	The project attempts to facilitate a unified energy system across the EU which is concurrently based on decentralised production and distributed flexibility exploitation.	1/10/2020	30/9/2023
TwinERGY	Intelligent interconnection of prosumers in positive energy communities with twins of things for digital energy markets	The project develops a Digital Twin that optimises demand-side management while preserving the well-being of prosumers and their activity patterns and day-to-day operations.	1/11/2020	31/10/2023
TIGON	Towards Intelligent DC-based hybrid Grids Optimizing the network performance	The project focuses on new generation DC or hybrid grid paradigm that offers better potential to accommodate RES and other DC loads connected to energy storage and EVs.	1/9/2020	31/8/2024
BRIGHT	Boosting DR through increased community-level consumer engagement by combining Data-driven and blockChain technology Tools with social science approaches and multi-value service design	The project targets the energy community-based development of demand-side response through newly introduced technologies in the energy field, such as blockchain platforms, etc.	1/11/2020	31/10/2023
SERENE	Sustainable and Integrated Energy Systems in Local Communities	The project objective comprises the development and demonstration of energy community solutions that are integrated, digitalised and sustainable.	1/5/2021	30/4/2025
iFLEX	Intelligent Assistants for Flexibility Management	The project targets prosumer empowerment and facilitation of the participation in DR transactions through a SW agent, the so-called “iFLEX Assistant” that connects consumers with energy system.	1/11/2020	31/10/2023

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SENDER	Sustainable Consumer engagement and demand response	The project focuses on next-generation DR and home-automation solutions that will facilitate a consumer-centric transformation of the energy markets. In parallel consumer engagement through co-creation methodologies is applied.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024
ISLANDER	Accelerating the decarbonisation of island energy systems	Showcasing the island of Borkum, the project attempts to develop efficient and holistic solutions in order to enable the effective integration of RES in islanded parts of the energy system.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024
HYPERRIDE	Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of DC Equipment	The project focus on innovative DC and hybrid energy grids contributing in the development and implementation of such solutions.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024
HESTIA	Holistic dEmand response Services for European residentTIAI communities	The project aspires to provide compound services (energy & non-energy) in terms of an innovative demand response framework and with a concurrent holistic approach combining decentralised generation and demand on local level.	1/11/2020	31/10/2023
RESPONSE	integRatEd Solutions for PPositive eNErgy and reSilient CitiEs	The project aims to provide positive energy to energy districts based on innovative solution demonstrators in 2 Lighthouse cities 6 Fellow cities.	1/10/2020	30/9/2025
ALIGHT	Copenhagen Airport: a Lighthouse for the introduction of sustainable aviation solutions for the future	The attempts to contribute to the global requirements of greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction. The project demonstrations will comprise two sustainability solutions.	1/11/2020	31/10/2024

From the abovementioned list of projects that present promising collaborative potential with the ACCEPT project, a strong synergy has been developed with the project ReDREAM, SENDER, iFLEX, and HESTIA. Details on this synergy and its outputs to date are included in another section of this report.

Regular events to be used as collaboration platforms

ACCEPT is using all the already established platforms for networking and feedback exchange among different R&I projects and invested stakeholders. Such platforms are offered through signature events, such as EUSEW, ENLIT, Sustainable Places, etc. Following a short overview of these platforms in Table 4.

Table 4 Major established collaboration platforms considered by ACCEPT

<p>The logo for Sustainable Energy Week features three overlapping circles in shades of green and blue. To the right, the text 'SUSTAINABLE ENERGY WEEK' is written in blue and green. Below this, it says 'An initiative of the European Commission' with the European Union flag.</p>	<p>European Sustainability Energy Week constitutes a Policy Conference focused on RES and the concept of Energy Efficiency. It is organised and coordinated by the European Commission aiming to pave the way towards 2030 and 2050 visions of energy system decarbonisation.</p> <p>It represents a highly inclusive platform that attempts to gather R&I projects together with invested stakeholders in order to make elaborations in sustainability and respective policy frameworks that can foster it.</p> <p>The event includes different platforms, such as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Networking Village ii. Energy Fair iii. Energy Lab iv. Energy Talks <p>which offer networking opportunities and forge collaborations.</p>
<p>The logo for Enlit Europe features a circular arrangement of yellow dots of varying sizes, resembling a globe or a network. The text 'Enlit Europe' is written in white on a black background.</p>	<p>Enlit is one of the largest exhibitions within the EU and globally that focuses on Smart Energy Innovation, Utilities and Power Generation. It accommodates a multitude of events, focus groups and fairs that connect the stakeholder community and provide a platform where industry meets research and innovation. The ultimate target is to foster all aspects to a sound transition towards a new sustainable energy landscape.</p>
<p>The logo for Sustainable Places features a stylized blue line drawing of a city skyline with a cloud-like shape above it. To the right, the text 'SUSTAINABLE PLACES' is written in blue.</p>	<p>Sustainable Places annual conference constitutes a platform that attempts to showcase the most significant results from H2020 projects in the research areas of building automation, sustainable urban design, utilities and energy industry. Given the wide participation of R&I projects, the event offers a unique collaboration and feedback exchange platform.</p>

Apart from the already established platforms, ACCEPT has joined forces with some of the projects that were shortlisted in Table 3, in order to create an addition collaboration platform. The projects were selected based on their similarities and the scientific common grounds and an overview of them is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 H2020 project collaboration platform co-organised by ACCEPT

The joined platform aspires to conduct a meticulous work during the projects' lifetime in order to ensure collaboration at multiple levels, e.g., user requirements, user engagement, solution development and deployment, impact assessment, conclusions, etc. The main structure of the platform will include the following aspects:

- i. A pool /repository of common material of the H2020 projects including the focus areas of national legislation / regulatory frameworks on energy communities, market codes/regulations and good practices on stakeholder engagement.
- ii. The co-organisation of key dissemination workshops on annual basis in the frame of conference platforms such as the Sustainable Places.
- iii. Systematic work on finetuning and homogenisation of the business and use cases of the various project, where applicable, in order to ensure compatibility and easy comparability of project outcomes, impact assessment methodologies, etc.
- iv. Regular, thematic meetings between the projects during the different research phases.
- v. The culmination of the projects' synergy into a whitepaper on the best practices for the creation of energy communities in Europe and the experiences of engaging with end users and energy stakeholders from each project.

2.2. Internal reporting and evaluation of collaboration activities

Given that there are multiple collaboration attempts carried out by the coordinator and by several other consortium members, there is a need to establish an internal reporting process in order to summarise the results, communicate them internally to the consortium but also report them in the regular technical project management reports.

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In terms of internal management of ACCEPT participation in BRIDGE, Hypertech Energy Labs, as the coordinator and leader of WP10, will have a horizontal and supervisory role. Therefore, the partner should be included in all the communications with the BRIDGE initiative.

When the project is requested to provide task-specific feedback to BRIDGE or fill-in a specific survey/questionnaire, the following partners should be involved:

- i. The assigned WG-TF member(s) from ACCEPT
- ii. Hypertech Energy Labs as the leader of BRIDGE activities.
- iii. In case that the results of an ACCEPT deliverable need to be shared, the leader of the respective task should also be involved.

Finally, any activity within BRIDGE (meetings, material, etc.) should be communicated to EEE (as the dissemination and communication lead) and disseminated. In order to facilitate internal communication, a special mailing list has been created under the e-mail address: wp10-bridge@accept-project.eu.

3. Report of ACCEPT Collaboration Activities

3.1. BRIDGE activities M19-M30

Within the last 12 months of the project, ACCEPT has participated in the annual BRIDGE procedures and actions, including attendance of most of the initiative’s meetings, such as the General Assembly in March 2023 and thematic working group and Task Forces discussions. Further details on the events as well as the project’s participation and contribution are provided below.

BRIDGE General Assembly 2023 Meeting (March 28-30 2023)

The annual BRIDGE General Assembly Meeting for 2023 took place over three days between the 28th and the 30th of March. The meeting brought together multiple partners from different European research projects on the fields of Smart Grid, Energy Storage and Islands & Digitalization. More than 300 registrations were completed, and around 75 people were on-site and more than 150 online.

In this year’s GA around 60 new projects joined the initiative, thus a new way for interacting with the new projects was used instead. Project posters were created and presented at the GA premises, allowing the participants to speak directly with the new project coordinators that were available throughout the meeting period. Regarding the collaboration of BRIDGE with other initiatives, ETIP Smart Networks for Energy Transition (ETIP SNET), the Smart Grid Task Force (SGTF), the Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) and 2ZERO Partnership initiatives, shared interesting presentations about their latest work. Moreover, the plenary on International Cooperation jointly presented by DG ENER, RTD, JRC, and the Bridge “IElectrix project” which has activities in India (and in which, Hypertech is a partner), gave an insight into the international engagement. ENTSO-E and the EU DSO Entity introduced their joint preparatory work for promoting digital twins of the electricity grids.

As of the time of the meeting, BRIDGE comprised 57 ongoing research projects, and 42 have been already completed. The completed ones were briefly presented their main accomplishments and shared their lessons learned and recommendations for the new projects joining the initiative, which have been recorded by the ACCEPT beneficiaries attending the meeting and shared with the consortium.

The main sessions covered the work the BRIDGE working groups did on Data Management, Regulation, Consumer and Citizen Engagement and Business models. The details of the agenda of the event can be seen in Figure 6.

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DAY 1: 28/03/2023	12:00 – 17:00	PLENARY 1 – JOIN HERE		
	17:00 – 19:00	Networking cocktail		
DAY 2: 29/03/2023	09:00 – 10:30	Focus Topic – Setting up a common European data space for energy JOIN HERE		
	10:30 – 11:15	Coffee Break + New Bridge projects posters session		
	11:15 – 13:30	Parallel session 1 BUSINESS MODELS WG JOIN HERE	Parallel session 2 CONSUMER & CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT WG JOIN HERE	
		Lunch Break		
	14:30 – 17:30	Parallel session 3 REGULATION WG JOIN HERE	Parallel session 4 DATA MANAGEMENT WG JOIN HERE	
DAY 3: 30/03/2023	09:00 – 12:30	PLENARY 2 – JOIN HERE		

Figure 6 : Structure of agenda of the BRIDGE GA 2023 [1]

The agenda of the second day's parallel session 4 (Data Management Working group) of BRIDGE GA 2023, is shown in Figure 7.

Parallel Session 4: DATA MANAGEMENT WG			
The session will present and discuss about the preliminary Data Management WG results, its learnings, and potential recommendations. The discussion will also allow the WG: (1) to agree on the main directions to complete the on-going work; and (2) to identify relevant subsequent activities for the 2023-2024 period			
14:30 – 14:35	Welcome	Time for remote participants to connect	ALL
14:35 – 14:45	Introduction	Objectives and scope of the session Expected outcomes	Olivier Genest, (DM WG Chair)
14:45 – 15:05	BRIDGE use case repository	Current status – 5'	Lola Alacreu (ETRA)
		Discussion on the right approach for testing phase and roll-out – 10'	All (led by Lola Alacreu)
		Conclusion & next steps – 5'	Lola Alacreu (ETRA)
15:05 – 16:00	Data Exchange Reference Architecture (DERA)	Current results from each subaction – 15'	Kalle Kukkk & sub-action leaders
		Discussion on the conclusions and next steps for each of the sub-actions – 30'	All (led by Kalle Kukkk & sub-action leaders)
		Conclusion & next steps – 10'	Kalle Kukkk (Elering)
16:00 – 16:35	Reference Framework	Current status – 10'	Olivier Genest, DM WG Chair
		Discussion on the new and updated Generic Business Processes (GBPs), including Settlement subprocess – 15'	All (led by Olivier Genest & sub-action leaders)
		Discussion on the next steps & conclusion – 10'	All (led by Olivier Genest & sub-action leaders)
16:35 – 17:30	Interoperability of home appliances	Current status & answers from the survey – 15'	Krzysztof Piotrowski (IHP)
		Discussion on how the home appliances interoperability is tackled by the projects and how BRIDGE could support them – 25'	All (led by Krzysztof Piotrowski)
		Conclusion & next steps – 5'	Krzysztof Piotrowski (IHP)

Figure 7: Agenda of the parallel session 4 on the 29th of March 2023 [1]

During the aforementioned sessions held as part of the GA meeting, the work carried out by the WGs was for 2022-2023 was presented. This included the contributions that representatives of the ACCEPT

project made in this period, such as the reports released on Action 3 and 5 of the Data Management WG and the report culminating the work on engagement indicators by the Consumer Engagement WG. Examples of such contributions are briefly mentioned below:

In the frame of the General Assembly, several thematic sessions were held that ACCEPT took the chance to participate. Indicatively, RINA-C participated to the Regulation WG (knowledge sharing sessions and review of 2022 report) and Hypertech Energy Labs provided inputs and feedback for the presentation “Current status & answers from the survey”, part of the session “interoperability of home appliances”. On behalf of ACCEPT project, Hypertech Energy Labs provided all the required inputs regarding the interoperability of project’s devices (online survey). In the survey, besides ACCEPT, 18 more projects participated: ELECTRON, ROBINSON, IANOS, Pocityf, X-FLEX, Re-Empowered, eNeuron, LocalRES, MAESHA, PRELUDE, TwinERGY, ACCEPT, HESTIA, InterConnect, TwinERGY, int:net, ebalance-plus, SYNERGY, EUniversal. Over 70 % of the answers involved control and monitoring of home appliances (Figure 8).

Summary of the survey responses

The responses in a nutshell

- 21 responses
- 19 projects: ELECTRON, ROBINSON, IANOS, Pocityf, X-FLEX, Re-Empowered, eNeuron, LocalRES, MAESHA, PRELUDE, TwinERGY, ACCEPT, HESTIA, InterConnect, TwinERGY, int:net, ebalance-plus, SYNERGY, EUniversal
- Over 70 % of the answers involve control and monitoring of home appliances

- Only limited details on the appliances (separate excel file)

bridge

These initiatives are funded by

Figure 8: Indicative slide from the presentation “Current status & answers from the survey”, part of the session “interoperability of home appliances”. The ACCEPT project participated in the survey with 18 other projects

The key takeaways of the 2023 BRIDGE General Assembly are also summarized in the BRIDGE website links below:

- BRIDGE General Assembly 2023 conclusions and next steps:
https://bridge-smart-grid-storage-systems-digital-projects.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-05/BRIDGE%202023%20GA%20-%20Conclusions_FINAL%20VERSION.pdf

More details on the ACCEPT involvement in the BRIDGE initiative will also be provided in the following paragraph, which summarises the generic contribution of ACCEPT to BRIDGE WGs and TFs.

The repository is currently active and research projects can upload their uses cases. This allows a common approach between different projects to materialize through the sharing of data and information. The use case repository can be found in the EIRIE platform (credentials required): <https://ses.jrc.ec.europa.eu/eirie/en/>. A second test, of the UC repository is expected to start soon using the provided feedback on the submission process. ACCEPT has agreed to be a member of the validation team for the Use Case repository of the DMWG’s Action 1.

Reference Framework - Data Management Working Group, June 2023 (reports 2022-23)

The last version of the Reference Framework report highlights the topic of “Interoperability of flexibility assets”, which was initiated in the BRIDGE GA 2020 (March) and was included in the first version of the report in April 2021. The report presents seven Generic Business Processes (4 new GBPs added in the last report) and details regarding the Settlement subprocess. It also highlights three main findings and recommendations that are related to i) the alignment and adherence of projects solutions to existing standards and on-going initiatives, ii) expectations and benefits deriving from the identified Generic Business Processes, and iii) the need for further understanding of implementing the Settlement subprocess.

The ACCEPT project has not only provided contributions to the specific WG action (action 3), through the completion of specific surveys, but has also helped with the analysis of inputs received from all participating projects and is included in the co-author list of the relevant BRIDGE report. More precisely, ACCEPT provided its business process diagram for the Settlement subprocess regarding the role of flexibility provider and the relevant flexibility scenarios of the project (P2P exchange, Explicit DR, Implicit DR). Details for the set of rules applied in the flexibility scenarios, which are included in the smart contracts, are also provided and are known as Service Level Agreements (SLAs). The smart contracts are made between the flex service provider and the flex provider. These rules are the base for the settlement subprocess presented in the figure below (Figure 10).

Settlement subprocess 2 - ACCEPT project

Figure 10: Settlement subprocess of the ACCEPT project

Interoperability of home appliances Report 2022-2023 (Action #5)

In May 2023, another report of BRIDGE was released regarding the interoperability of home appliances. The ACCEPT project participated to this report as an editor, being responsible for reviewing, revising, and improving the content of the report. Moreover, Hypertech Energy Labs and IsZEB participated in the preparation meetings and consultation rounds.

The report defined some common ground on the interoperability of home appliances and provided insights in the approaches used by the BRIDGE projects. The problems faced in that respect, and the implemented solutions were described. For this purpose, ACCEPT along with other 17 BRIDGE projects, responded to an online survey regarding the interoperability of the home appliances of the project. Over 72% of the projects responded, involve home appliances. In this way, the state of things in the running BRIDGE projects was outlined. The survey constituted of two parts: the project level part and the device level part. The one part covered more general aspects of the appliances, while the second one, specific details of the used devices. The aim was to use the survey's data in order to create a repository/database, which will be used by other and/or new projects in the future. However, although conclusions on the interoperability of the appliances can be drawn, the survey will be continued in the following period of Action#5, as limited responses were received in some parts of it [5].

REGULATION WG

No updates for the period M19-M30

BUSINESS MODELS WG

No updates for the period M19-M30

CONSUMER AND CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT WG

Engagement Strategy Questionnaire

In January 2023, ACCEPT filled-in a questionnaire for the sub-group of Strategies of Engagement in the CCE WG, which is working on a deliverable "engagement handbook", where ACCEPT is aimed to be one of the project examples. ACCEPT beneficiaries UCC and SIN contributed, providing details on the main elements of the engagement strategy, the implemented period and the kind of settings applied. Moreover, information provided about the main target groups, the number of citizens engaged, and the countries/cities applied. Finally, the recognised success factors and barriers were presented and a link with photos and videos from the ACCEPT project website was provided (<https://www.accept-project.eu/library>).

In M27, the ACCEPT's consortium member SIN participated in the consumer and citizen engagement working group, and contributed to the writing of the annual report 2023. Inputs for an abstract submission to the sustainable places conference entitled "A framework for measuring stakeholder engagement in energy transitions projects" were also provided.

Best practices on citizen consumer engagement - Case study #8 report

In M29, ACCEPT provided contributions in the context of "Best practices on citizen consumer engagement - Case study #8" report, which will probably be released in the first half of 2023. ACCEPT provided inputs regarding a remote capacity building workshop for the project partners, in order to increase the understanding and knowledge of engagement strategies, within the consortium. Moreover, a community stakeholder matrix mapping analysis was provided, which determines the role each stakeholder was going to have. This type of analysis considers stakeholders along the dimensions of interest and influence and is based on [6]. Moreover, key insights on how to increase the users' engagement were provided along with expected barriers, based on the experience acquired during the

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project. Strategies to motivate user engagement were also described, with key examples from the ACCEPT’s pilot sites. Inputs were further provided regarding the development toolkits and serious design games, to facilitate the exchanges with citizen consumers. In this content, the persona methodology developed by SIN beneficiary of ACCEPT was described. Several recognized factors (social, economic, environmental and political) that can promote sustainability were briefly mentioned. Finally, acceptance and satisfaction surveys graphs conducted within ACCEPT (D7.1), have been integrated in the report.

BRIDGE Initiative meetings

Some of the key BRIDGE initiative meetings that the ACCEPT consortium has attended within the period between M19-M30, can be found in the table below.

Table 5 BRIDGE Initiative, indicative meetings with ACCEPT representatives (M19-M30)

Meeting	Attendees	Date
BRIDGE SG Indicators meeting	EEE, SIN	07/07/2022
Participation in BRIDGE sub group: Indicators of engagement	SIN, EEE	18/08/2022
SNET Webinar Digitally enabled renewable energy communities	Hypertech	07/09/2022
BRIDGE DMWG kick-off 2022	Hypertech, IsZEB	22/09/2022
BRIDGE Data Management WG Action #5 kick-off	Hypertech, IsZEB	07/11/2022
BRIDGE Data Management WG Action #5 meeting	Hypertech	18/11/2022
BRIDGE SG Indicators meeting	EEE, SIN	20/11/2022
BRIDGE Data Management WG Action #3 Reference Framework meeting	Hypertech, IsZEB	09/12/2022
BRIDGE Data Management WG - Sub-action 3.2 Meeting	Hypertech, IsZEB	23/01/2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG Action #3 Reference Framework meeting	Hypertech, IsZEB	30/01/2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG Action #3 Reference Framework meeting	Hypertech	17/02/2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG Action #5 meeting	Hypertech	28/02/2023
BRIDGE WG Meeting – Consumer and Citizen Engagement	EEE	01/03/2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG Action #5 meeting	Hypertech, IsZEB	01/03/2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG Action #3 Reference Framework meeting	Hypertech	06/03/2023
BRIDGE General Assembly 2023 – participation in meeting for GA presentation	Hypertech, RINA-C	22/03/2023
BRIDGE General Assembly 2023	Hypertech, RINA-C, IsZEB, EEE	28-30/03/2023
BRIDGE DMWG kick-off 2023	Hypertech, IsZEB	28/06/2023

3.2. Collaboration activities with other projects (synergies) M19-M30

Projects collaboration under the call: LC-SC3-EC-3-2020 - Consumer engagement and demand response

Sustainable places conference 2022

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Initially, the possibility for partners to participate in the event was discussed in several calls with sister projects, where the main topic and format of the session to be held, as well as the provisional agenda were agreed. On behalf of the ACCEPT project, the BRIDGE representatives Hypertech, SIN, MIWenergia, UCC and ESR of the ACCEPT consortium participated, along with EEE beneficiary which supported the organization of the workshop. Moreover, decisions on format and modification of the session were made, along with discussion panel and the round table discussion points (M20). It was decided that the ACCEPT project would chair and moderate the workshop. The Sustainable places conference 2022 was held on the 8th of September 2022 (M21), where ACCEPT participated in the workshop on "Fostering user engagement for innovative demand response for effective flexibility". The recording for the session is available [online](#). Moreover, discussions for a common paper (Sustainable Places) were conducted and finally the open letter for Sustainable Places 2022 session prepared, and released with the other four projects (M22).

Figure 11 Sustainable Places 2022 workshop with ACCEPT sister projects on 'Fostering user engagement for innovative demand response for effective flexibility'

ETIP SNET Webinar

ACCEPT participated in ETIP SNET Webinar - Digitally enabled renewable energy communities: The role of citizens in the clean energy transition was held on the 07th September 2022 (<https://smart-networks-energy-transition.ec.europa.eu/events/current-and-past-events/etip-snet-webinar-digitally-enabled-renewable-energy-communities>). The webinar organised by DG ENERGY and REScoop and had three main sessions: 1) Digital enabling of renewable energy communities, 2) Customers (prosumers and consumers) involvement, 3) The role of youth continuous education in energy and digitalization. ACCEPT contributed in M24, by answering in a questionnaire on how it contributes to Research, Development and Innovation.

E-LAND project 2020 (24th June 2022)

In June 2022 the Forum focused on the social acceptance of renewable energies and ambitious climate policies, in collaboration with the ACCEPT project. A workshop was conducted on "B2B energy communities" led by Beatrice Petrovich (University of St.Gallen). The workshop presented two real cases where a group of neighbouring energy users, collectively self-consumed locally produced renewable energy. The key learnings from the implemented engagement strategy were highlighted. Minna Kuivalainen from SIN beneficiary, member of the ACCEPT consortium, presented the E-LAND pilot site WALQA Technology Park in Spain. Moreover, another partner of ACCEPT, Daniele Farrace from AEM beneficiary, illustrated the ARENA Innovation Community in Switzerland, one of the living labs of the ACCEPT project [7].

1st POWERPOOR EU inspiring event

CIRCE beneficiary from the ACCEPT consortium presented the project in the context of the PowerPoor project event, held on the 30th of November 2022 (<https://powerpoor.eu/news-events/1st-powerpoor-eu-inspiring-event>). The concept of the event was the alleviation energy poverty by empowering citizens and by enabling women to play their part in democratising energy. This event aimed to develop support programmes and schemes for energy-poor citizens and encourage the use of alternative financing schemes to tackle energy poverty. It brought together experts highlighting results and opportunities in the energy sector, sharing knowledge and lessons learned. In a separate Pitching Session, participants were able to present their projects for 10 minutes and to find potential partners.

Figure 12 1st PowerPoor EU inspiring event, agenda

Figure 13: Paola Mazzucchelli from CIRCE, presenting ACCEPT project at 1st PowerPoor EU inspiring event

ENLIT Europe 2022 Smart and Green Energy Communities event

ACCEPT participated in the ENLIT Europe 2022 Smart and Green Energy Communities event, held on the 30th of November 2022. Discussions were conducted with ReDREAM project about their UI, communications strategy, technologies developed and tested, along with their engagement strategy. Hypertech (project coordinator) presented the project, giving at first an overview and its main aspects (Figure 14). Moreover, the ACCEPT solution was described focusing on user engagement strategies and empowerment of energy communities. Finally, information for the pilot sites was given along with key challenges and lessons learnt until that phase of the project (M23). The consortium members that joined the event were from AEM, MIWenergia, QUE, Mytilineos and Hypertech beneficiaries (Figure 15).

Figure 14: ENLIT event 2022 - presentation of the ACCEPT project

AEM, MIWenergia, QUE and Mytilneos beneficiaries were present at the project’s stand to discuss the Living Lab activities of the project with interested parties, providing details for the four pilot sites of ACCEPT.

Figure 15: ENLIT event 2022, members of the ACCEPT consortium from AEM, MIWenergia, QUE, Mytilneos and Hypertech beneficiaries

In the context of the event, a podcast for ACCEPT project was created as an episode of the EU Projects Zone podcast. Areti Ntaradimou discussed with Ismini Dimitriadou (Hypertech) about the digital toolbox that ACCEPT intends to develop and deliver. The ACCEPT project was described in a nutshell. Moreover, the discussion highlighted the covered needs of the EU energy grid by the project and revealed

difficulties during the engagement process. Finally, the talk concluded with regulatory issues and recommendations, on how EU and the local authorities could help ACCEPT achieve its goals. The episode was released on the 24th of March 2023 (link: <https://www.enlit.world/energy-communities/the-eu-projects-zone-podcast-accept-with-ismini-dimitriadou/>).

Paper submission to the Open Research Europe platform

In January 2023, the ACCEPT project through UCC beneficiary, participated in the submission of a paper with title "Lessons learnt during the workshop "Empowerment of citizens: fostering user engagement for innovative demand response for effective flexibility"". The paper was submitted to the Open Research Europe, which is an innovative open access publishing platform of the EU. The paper has been reviewed and approved with reservations from one peer reviewer (June 2023 - <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/3-1>). To pass the peer review process, it needs either two 'Approved' statuses, or two 'Approved with Reservations' statuses and one 'Approved' status from the reviewers.

The paper describes the discussions held during of the workshop "Fostering user engagement for innovative demand response for effective flexibility" celebrated during the 10th edition of the Sustainable Places 2022 conference. This event was organised in a hybrid format in Nice, France, from the 6th September to 9th September 2022, in which the sister projects iFLEX, ACCEPT, HESTIA, SENDER, and ReDREAM participated. This open letter follows the format used by the workshop held in Sustainable places 2022 (SP2022): the questions were asked by the moderator and the answers were given by sister projects' representatives, together summarising the collaborative work performed by the five projects (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/3-1>).

The peer review process time-consuming, thus it still needs time to confirm if the paper will be officially published.

SCORE project

In M27, Hypertech Energy Labs contacted RINA-C beneficiary for a possible new synergy with the SCORE project under the framework of the Horizon Results Booster (HRB). The kick-off meeting was finally held during M28 with the participation of RINA-C, which keeps providing updates to the ACCEPT consortium.

ENCLUDE H2020 project

Moreover, UCC beneficiary through its work on the ENCLUDE H2020 project, is liaising with the EC2 H2020 project on actioning energy citizenship ideas around the energy transition (similar to EC2's "Community Energy Academy", the ENCLUDE has developed the "ENCLUDE Academy for Energy Citizen Leadership" (<https://encludeproject.eu/enclude-academy-energy-citizen-leadership>), which has engaged with its sister projects while recruiting participants etc. The academy is now nearing its successful conclusion and outputs from it will assist the sister projects on their efforts). UCC's work on the ENCLUDE project continues to inform its efforts in ACCEPT till now.

White paper 2023

Regarding white paper for sister projects for the period between M19-M30, regular online telcos were initially conducted, to discuss and decide on the content and the structure of the paper. Preliminary inputs of the ACCEPT project were requested and provided in M25 (February 2022), participating in the relevant meeting, to discuss the next steps. Subsequently, another meeting was held on the 3rd of May 2023, where particular guidelines and deadlines were provided.

In May 2023, the ACCEPT project submitted all required inputs in detail in a report of 31 pages. Contributions asked and received from pilot leaders (ESR, AEM, Mytilineos, LaSolar) and UCC, SIN

beneficiaries of the project. Briefly the sections filled in based in the provided guidelines, were the following:

- User recruitment methodology (initial phases of the user engagement strategy) → What was your plan?
- Type of users being recruited in the project → Who is the user that we are aiming to engage? How are we taking into consideration aspects/factors such as the acceptability and affordability of the solutions, gender dimension, etc.? Which actor (local utility company or public authority vs. external partner) is implementing the recruitment/engagement activities? Importance of their relationship with the potential users.
- Actual recruitment process that has taken place in the project, with practical examples from the pilot sites → What challenges did you face? How did you overcome them? How did this affect the overall engagement strategy? Which recruitment activities worked well (in a specific context)?
- References to use for introduction → relevant references used in the report (and the corresponding deliverables) were included, to provide material for the introduction – literature review, of the white paper.
- Highlights of the main benefits of the recruitment/engagement strategies that you are applying in your project (ACCEPT)→ benefits of workshops - applied methodology, and benefits for the pilot sites
- Key recommendations that should be brought forward → recommendations provided based on the experience acquired so far.
- Visual materials (photos, infographics, graphs, etc.) to make the white paper more attractive to the eye → photos, infographics, graphs from project’s pilot sites during the pilot site visits and user engagement activities.

Part of the visual material included in the ACCEPT inputs for the white paper report are presented below (Figure 16 - Figure 18).

Figure 16: Meeting with the local energy expert from the Murcia region in the Spanish pilot

Figure 17: Dutch pilot site representatives provided a tour of the Lanxmeer community to WP3 leaders

Figure 18: Swiss pilot representatives providing a tour of the assets in the Massagno community

Workshop at Sustainable Places (SP) 2023 (June 14th-16th)

The ACCEPT project responded successfully to the call for a common workshop with its sister projects, where presentations from each project would be delivered and a round table discussion would follow. The presentation was held on the 14th of June 2023, where MIWenergia partner represented ACCEPT. A project overview of the project and the main steps of the implemented engagement methodology were presented. Co-creation activities focused on C-App and feedback received by the engaged users. The presentation included tools and platforms developed for user engagement and analytical explanation of the learning points during the engagement process of the ACCEPT’s pilot sites. A round table session was conducted as well, where all participants had the chance to express their ideas and bring their perspectives. Indicative visual material pictures from the workshop are presented below (Figure 19- Figure 21).

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Figure 19: ACCEPT participation in Sustainable places 2023, where ACCEPT was represented by MIWenergia beneficiary

Figure 20: ACCEPT participation in Sustainable places 2023, presentation on behalf of the project: Pablo Barrachina MIWenergia)

Figure 21: Sustainable places 2023, round table session

Responses to the questionnaire of the WHY project (M22)

Beneficiaries LaSolar, AEM, Hypertech and MIWenergia responded to a survey conducted by the WHY project (and UDEUSTO in particular) aimed to increase understanding on 'Why do Consumers participate in the Energy Transition'. The briefing on the survey was as follows:

„Survey: Why Do Consumers Participate in the Energy Transition“

In the framework of the of the H2020-WHY (why-h2020.eu), H2020-PARITY (parity-h2020.eu/), H2020-SMARTLIVINGEPC (cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069639) and H2020-ATELIER (smartcity-atelier.eu) projects we are assessing the **determinants (factors)** that lead consumers to participate in the energy transition in order to create better policies for them. The focus is on the reasons behind investments in flexibility markets (e.g. PV panels or batteries), energy efficiency (e.g. building insulation), mobility (e.g. electric vehicles) and energy conservation (e.g. sharing economy). The objective of this survey is to build a set of archetypes (a very typical example of a certain person which is present in the collective unconscious) that characterise as much as possible the European population when investing in technologies or behaviours or products related to the energy transition.

To take the survey, please click in the following link:

[https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Investment Arquetypes 2022](https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Investment_Arquetypes_2022)

Responses to the SET Plan questionnaire (M22)

In October, beneficiary LaSolar responded to a Call for Evidence (under the framework of a relevant public consultation) by the European Commission on the revision of the SET Plan, which needs to be updated for ensuring alignment with the latest political context with regards to the widespread deployment of smart energy technologies.

The Engagement Handbook of the Strategies of Engagemetn SG

Partners UCC, SIN and EEE joined forces and responded to a call for the collection of data, knowledge and experiences from EU-funded projects from the engagement strategies they followed. Such experiences and knowledge included learnings (lessons learned), best practices on customer/citizen engagement and possible identified barriers.

Other collaborations

Synergies have also been developed with projects that go beyond H2020 and the BRIDGE initiative in order to raise awareness on the ACCEPT project and potentially maximise its impact later in the process. Such a synergy was established with the Erasmus+/Knowledge Alliances Project “GrEnFIn”, through MIWenergia beneficiary, a project which aims to train Professionals and Students to become Sustainable Energy Experts.

3.3. Planned collaboration activities for the next period

The next steps of ACCEPT with regards to the BRIDGE initiative comprise the regular participation in all WGs and TFs either through answering surveys, provision of written contribution or participation in meetings. In parallel, ACCEPT aspires to also participate in the General Assembly body of BRIDGE and contribute to material such as the BRIDGE newsletter, brochure, etc.

Concerning the collaboration with similar H2020 projects, ACCEPT intends to continue supporting the “thematic meetings” with HESTIA-iFLEX-REDREAM-SENDER. The identified next step list of the “consortium of projects” includes the following milestones:

1. Publication of the jointly prepared whitepaper and, possibly, coordinated dissemination efforts on key learnings included therein.
2. Publication of the paper with title “Lessons learnt during the workshop “Empowerment of citizens: fostering user engagement for innovative demand response for effective flexibility”, which is currently under peer-review.
3. Public and approved deliverable sharing.

Next steps also include establishing new synergies with innovation projects that share commonalities with the ACCEPT project and draw value out of those synergies.

4. Conclusions

BRIDGE constitutes an initiative of substantial importance for research and innovation Horizon projects attempting to harmonise their results, coordinate inputs and outputs in order to produce useful conclusions that contribute to the realisation of the roadmap towards the transition to a sustainable energy landscape with Smart Grids, Renewable Energy Sources and Energy Storage.

ACCEPT has been actively participating in BRIDGE structure and contributing with its tools, methodology and pilot testbeds to overcome cross-cutting issues that constitute obstacles towards innovation. Given the project objectives and challenges, it seems essential to utilise BRIDGE feedback on business modelling and EU regulation. On the other hand, given the project's wide demand response pilot validation framework including different cultural, geographical and socioeconomic contexts, it can provide valuable feedback to BRIDGE elaboration. This "win-win" relationship between BRIDGE and ACCEPT project will be explored in WP10 and more specifically in T10.1.

The collaboration strategy of the project is defined and presented herein in D10.3, which is the third deliverable of WP10 and constitutes an updated version of ACCEPT D10.2 delivered in M18. Based on the updated DoA provisions [2], further activities regarding BRIDGE and wider collaboration attempts will be documented in the last deliverable 10.4.

Besides the participation in the BRIDGE activities, which have already started with the General Assembly of March 2021, the WG & TF discussions and the contribution to the brochure of 2021, ACCEPT has also initiated a horizontal project collaboration along with HESTIA-iFLEX-REDREAM-SENDER. This permanent project platform includes the creation of a common e-repository to be utilised as knowledge hub and means of feedback exchange, as well as the arrangement of joint dissemination and communication events utilising renowned and well-established platforms, such as EUSEW, Sustainable Places, Enlit, etc. Finally, all projects decided to arrange a series of "thematic meetings" in order to discuss their different approaches and methodologies, to harmonise their views and jointly elaborate on outcomes, and also work collaboratively on drafting and publishing a whitepaper for sharing the best practices for creating an energy community in the EU, based on experience from the pilot trials in the Netherlands, Greece, Italy, Spain and Finland.

In the terms of next steps, ACCEPT intends to follow-up all WGs and General Assemblies of BRIDGE and contribute to any surveys or reports required. The project will also support the joint collaboration platform that has been created by the five Demand Response & Energy Community-related H2020 projects. Finally, the ACCEPT consortium will actively seek further opportunities for establishing strategic synergies with other projects through which their mutual value can be added.

Through its meticulous and well-defined research methodology, but also through its open and collaborative approach, ACCEPT attempts to widely communicate its innovative framework and maximise its impact in the pilot sites and among the various stakeholder groups.

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Annex 1– ENLIT 2022 Smart and Green Energy Communities (30.11.2022)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

European Commission | Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation

ENLIT Europe 2022
Smart and Green Energy Communities
Ismini Dimitriadou, Hypertech (project coordinator)

Jan 2021 - June 2024

Project Overview

D10.3 – Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v3

ACCEPT in a nutshell

3

Basic Project Timeline

4

DIGITAL TOOLBOX & INNOVATIVE DIGITAL SERVICES

The ACCEPT solution

5

DEMONSTRATION & VALIDATION AT FOUR PILOT SITES

4 LIVING LABS

Benefits for Energy Communities

- Increase of community energy self-sufficiency
- Access to new revenue streams
- P2P energy and flexibility transactions
- Offer compound services to their energy community members

Benefits to Community Members

- Energy and cost savings
- Easy smart living (increase of comfort and convenience)
- Increase of energy awareness

Challenges

- COVID-19 confinement measures affecting engagement activities and project resourcing
- Global microchip shortage
- EU energy crisis transforming energy market and tariff schemes (Spanish example)
- Fragmentation of EU policies & transposition to national legislation (Energy Communities, Demand - Response, distributed generation)

Key challenges and lessons learnt

Lessons learnt

- Cultural differences among Energy Communities require different engagement approaches / different drivers for participation in project
- Fixed energy tariffs prohibit application of implicit DR schemes (and alleviation of grid constraints)
- Emergency measures of EC for tackling energy crisis leads to transitional effect delaying the widespread penetration of household DR
- Learning from installations: Planning is your friend! And accuracy is your best ally!
- Start your participants' recruitment from a large pool of people!

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Thank you for your attention

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"The Ecological Neighbourhood"

Culemborg, Netherlands

- Main participation driver**
- Increase of community selfsufficiency
 - Sustainability

"The Residential Suburb"

Capriasca, Switzerland

- Main participation driver**
- Increase of grid stability
 - Increase of community selfsufficiency

"The Urban Community"

Murcia, Spain

- Main participation driver**
- Cost and energy savings for community members

"The Smart Village"

Aspra Spitia, Greece

- Main participation driver**
- Cost and energy savings for community members
 - Smart living for community members

Annex 2– Sustainable Places 2023

Workshop
Innovative solution and co-creation for effective implementation of demand response

14^o of June, 2023 - Madrid, Spain

sustainableplaces.eu

All projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme

Project Overview

Jan 2021 to June 2024 Project cost: 7.57M€
 EU contribution: 5.86M€

Grant Number	957781
Call	H2020-LC-SC3-2020-EC-ES-SCC Topic: LC-SC3-EC-3-2020 - Consumer engagement and demand response
16 Partners	HYPERTECH, CIRCE, SIN, QUE, CERTH, Witside, UCC, RINA-C, Mytilineos, ESB, EDBR, MWenergía, LaSolar, AEM, Viesgo, EEE
Pilots	Demonstration Site Greece, Spain, Netherlands and Switzer land Pre-Validation testbeds 2 testbeds in Greece, DSO historical data from Spain

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Importance of User Engagement and Co-creation

3-step engagement approach:

- Raising citizen awareness (info campaigns)
 - What is the energy transition
 - Why do citizens need to be involved
 - How can they benefit
- Making citizens part of the solution (co-creation campaigns)
 - Citizen empowerment
 - Solution meets main user requirements
- Keeping momentum up (feedback and continuous engagement campaigns)
 - Motivation is key
 - Feedback leads to improvements and identification of obstacles

User Involvement in Pilot Sites

- 38 households
- 40 households
- 42 households
- 32 residential apartments

Involvement of Users in Co-creation activities

Co-creation focused on **Citizen Application**:

- Consent form for participants to consent to use of their data
- Briefing document to participants explaining project and user testing
- Notes for pilot partners with guiding note on the user testing process
- Discussion guide: A detailed description of the agenda and instructions for the user testing session for pilot partners to follow
- System Usability Scale (SUS): A standard survey for participants to fill out which provides a quantitative assessment of the C-APP's usability
- Living labs: pilot partners met with the end-users on a 1-to-1 basis for user testing session (feedback on design and functionality of C-App)

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Results of User Engagement (Co-creation)

Useful outcomes of co-creation workshops:

- Feedback from end-users of each pilot site used for C-App improvements
- Alignment of real end-user needs and ACCEPT toolset
- Data produced from SUS during user testing show users' current opinions on C-APP and help track progress of C-APP development

Country	Number of participants	Average Score
Spain	4	86.25
Switzerland	3	37.50
Netherlands	11	32.73
Greece	20	66.25
Combined average		56.38

What they liked

- Summaries on the DR page
- Majority happy with content of homepage
- **Topology and device consumption section & graph**

What they disliked

- Community functions not useful or clear
- **Analytics section and graph too complex**
- Lack of customization (language, measurement units)

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Miro Board

Printed material

Tools and Platforms for User Engagement

Questionnaires and Surveys

Most valuable tool - Human interaction

Key Learning from Implemented Strategies

Learning Point 1

Key Learning from Implemented Strategies

Citizen hesitation to engage

- Lack of awareness about the issue (*Why* should I help?)
- Lack of awareness about /limited understanding of possible solutions (*How* can I help?)
- Lack of incentives to engage (What's in it *for me*?)
- Lack of trust from citizens (Is it *safe*? Does it *work*?)

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Learning Point 2

Key Learnings from Implemented Strategies

What has worked well with co-creation activities:

- Leveraging local social dynamics & networks of trust
 - Co-creation activities led by pilot leaders
- Effective communication targeting average citizen
 - All guidance documents in layman terms and local language
- Engagement boosting events
 - Pilot partners introduced pilot sites and participants to SSH partners (leading on the Living Labs)
- Web-based citizen application available for user testing
- Simple tools used for gathering user feedback

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Key Learnings from Implemented Strategies

Learning Point 3

- Co-creation is very hard
 - Engagement persistence
 - Communication gap
- Co-creation is necessary
 - Achieve fitness-for-purpose
 - Increase acceptance and replication potential
- Tangible short-term incentives seem critical to engage citizens and achieve early buy-in
 - Until the sustainable, long-term benefits to citizens become evident

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Thank you!

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